

PROCEEDINGS OF THE 1st NATIONAL
CONFERENCE ON ENGLISH LANGUAGE
TEACHING UPGRADE: A FOCUS ON FLUENCY

Ho Chi Minh City
University of Food Industry

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PROCEEDINGS

OF THE 1st NATIONAL CONFERENCE ON
ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING UPGRADE:

A FOCUS ON FLUENCY

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SCIENCE AND TECHNICS PUBLISHING HOUSE

WELCOME SPEECH

Dear researchers, scientists, lecturers and students!

First of all, on behalf of Ho Chi Minh city University of Food Industry, I warmly welcome all delegates to attend the conference “ELT Upgrade 2018: A Focus on Fluency”.

Ladies and Gentlemen,

In recent years, Vietnam has welcomed many important events influencing positively on the country’s economic and social developments. These events have opened the doors for Vietnam to enter into very potential but challenging markets. Therefore, education in general and language teaching in particular are facing unprecedented challenges.

In the context of Vietnam, it cannot be denied that English has been bearing its crucial position since Vietnam became the member of World Trade Organization in 2006, and the goal to enhance learners’ English proficiency has been included as one of the important objectives to English Language Education by the Ministry of Education and Training of Vietnam through National Foreign Languages 2020 Project. This project has paid a particular attention to improve the quality of the teaching and learning English in higher education. The MOET state that, “... most Vietnamese students graduating from... colleges and universities will be able to use a foreign language confidently in their daily communication, their study and work in an integrated, multi-cultural and multi-lingual environment...”. The project expects that upon university graduates (non-English major and English major students) can reach levels B1 and C1 of the Common European Framework of Reference for Language (CEFR), respectively. Therefore, English language proficiency is an important factor in the future competitiveness of Vietnam students within the globalized job market.

However, despite the government’s priority, the quality of teaching and learning English in Vietnamese higher education is a concern. Specifically, both English major and non-English major students have been criticized for having low levels of English proficiency. As the suppliers of intellectual labor force not only for the whole country, but also for the ASEAN community and even for the world in the future, with what should Vietnam universities and colleges equip themselves and their students for the next coming chances and challenges? Obviously, theories and practices of teaching and learning need to be reviewed, adapted and innovated to meet the growingly complex demands of a diverse range of learners.

Recognizing this, Ho Chi Minh City University of Food Industry held a conference on English education “ELT Upgrade 2018: A Focus on Fluency” with the aim of improving the quality of foreign language teaching. We expect that the conference is a stepping stone so that our career in teaching English can meet the demands of the international education market.

Ladies and Gentlemen,

2018 marks the 36th anniversary of HUFU's establishment and development. In the past years, HUFU has actively implemented the mechanism of self-reliance, comprehensive innovation and has a strong change. In order to improve the quality of training, English teaching and learning activities are always carried out by HUFU teachers and school managers. We have created the best conditions in teaching policy and environment; therefore, in recent years, the English teaching activities of HUFU have achieved important achievements, giving students the bravery, confidence in communication as well as ability to work in the international environment after graduation.

In conclusion, on behalf of the school's leaders, I would like to express my sincere thanks to all the delegates and teachers, especially the experts for their precious time and dedication. I wish the experts, delegates, teachers and students good health, happiness and success. Wish you a very pleasant day at HUFU.

Thank you!

Assoc. Prof., Nguyen Xuan Hoan, PhD.

The President of Ho Chi Minh City University of Food Industry

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On ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING UPGRADE:
A FOCUS ON FLUENCY (CELTU 2018)

December 1st, 2018

Conference Organizers

Foreign Language Center,
Ho Chi Minh City University of Food Industry, Vietnam (HUFI)

Organizing Committee

Assoc. Prof., Nguyen Xuan Hoan, PhD (Rector)
Ho Chi Minh City University of Food Industry

MSc. Tran Tin Nghi, M.A
Ho Chi Minh City University of Food Industry

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